

Effect of Working Capital Management on Business Solvency and Growth. A Case Study of Small and Medium Enterprises in the Manufacturing Sector In Kitwe District

Obrone Kalengo Simukoko¹ and Peter Silwimba^{2a}

¹School of Humanities and Business, Information and communication University, Lusaka, Zambia

²Risk Department National Savings and Credit Bank, Lusaka, Zambia

^aSchool of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia

^aCorresponding Author: Peter Silwimba, Email: silwimbap47@gmail.com

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 24th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: SME growth SMEs performance Manufacturing sector Small and medium enterprises Working capital management Solvency</p>	<p>This research study focused on the effects of working capital management (WCM) on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the manufacturing sector of Kitwe District, Zambia. The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of WCW on solvency and growth. The results from the Chi-square showed a strong significant relationship across all objectives, with p-values less than 0.05, which lead to the rejection of the null hypotheses. WCW had a very strong influence on solvency with a Pearson correlation of ($r = 0.920$, $p = 0.000$) showing that factors like efficient management of receivables, payables, and inventory have an effect on the strength of the long-term financial stability of SMEs. On the other hand, growth showed the strongest relationship with WCW with a correlation of ($r = 0.959$ ($p = 0.000$), this clearly shows that firms that effectively manage working capital are well prepared and positioned to expand their business operations and also increase market competition. This study concluded that WCW is an important factor for SMEs going concern and it acts as a source of resilience in the areas of solvency and general business growth. A well-blended working capital management framework secures continuity and efficiency. The findings in this study have highlighted that while the benefits are obvious, the adoption of best practice is low and hence it is recommended that business forums should be established to increase capacity building in SMEs and deliberate services to offer training and guides in the use of capital management practice must be available.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 background of the study

Working capital management implies the administration of a company's short-term assets and liabilities to make sure it maintains enough liquidity and funds to run its business operations well (Deloof, 2003). (Brealey, Myers, and Allen, 2019; Ross, Westerfield, and Jordan, 2022) Every business requires working capital for its survival. A solvent company has assets that exceed its liabilities sufficiently to reinvest in its growth. Solvency refers to a company's ability to fulfil its obligations. Assessment of a company's ability to pay its obligations such as to make interest and principal payments generally include analysis of the components of its financial structure (Brigham & Ehrhardt, 2020). The degree of solvency in a business is measured by the relationship between the assets, liabilities and equity of a business at a given point in time.

The company should determine the appropriate solvency levels in increasing profitability (Pandey, 2018). The COVID 19 pandemic made the liquidity of business worse as many business operations and supply chains were paused and limited and Zambia was not an exception, this phase brought in the concept of understating working capital in a new form and ensuring that business survives as it gets hit from economic shocks from different angles (World Bank, 2021).

Therefore, this study seeks to examine the effectiveness of working capital management on business performance among SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe District. The primary objective of WCM is to achieve optimal balance among its components as part of the overall corporate strategy to increase value for shareholders. WCM, or working capital management, is a crucial component of financial management and comprises choices about the quantity, composition, and financing of current assets. WCM involves making judgments regarding various aspects of cash investment, maintaining a specific amount of inventory, and managing receivables and payables accounts (Falope 2019).

1.2 statement of the problem

According to Khrawish (2020) WCM is essential to a company's long-term success. In order to effectively manage each component of working capital, firms must create clear policies. To enhance business performance, working capital components like cash, accruals, accounts receivable, accounts payable, marketable securities, and other sources of short-term financing must be efficiently managed. Mishandling working capital can lead to the collapse of these institutions. Poor management of working capital can be either because these companies over invest or under invest in working capital requirements. Over investment in working capital will reduce returns by increasing the amount of funds tied up in non-interest earnings short-term assets. On the other hand, insufficient investment in working capital, that is, overtrading, increases the company’s risk of financial distress and may lead to a company being technically insolvent as it may not be able to meet its obligations such as paying their debts on time, paying salaries, electricity bills, tax, water bills, and other expenses that they incur in the course of doing business (Garcia-Teruel & Martinez-Solano, 2020).

Even though existing literature has recognized a relationship between effective WCM and firm performance. There is still a research gap concerning how these principles apply specifically to SMEs operating within the Zambian manufacturing sector, mostly in Kitwe District. The economic environment, Zambia differ considerably from those in developed economies. Given this background, this study seeks to examine the effectiveness of working capital management on the business performance of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe District. Musonda (2020) observes that WCM is essential for any firm to survive because of its effects on a firm’s profitability and consequently its value. There is no doubt that the ultimate objective of any firm is to maximize profit. However, the preservation of the liquidity of a firm is an important objective too and it is the efficient management of the various components of working capital that helps to preserve liquidity.

1.3 Research Objectives

The general and specific objectives of this study are as presented in the sections below.

1.3.1 General Objective

Effect of working capital management on business Solvency and Growth. A case study of small and medium enterprises in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives:

- i. To examine the effect of working capital management on solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.
- ii. To establish the effect working capital management on growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

1.3.3 Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of working capital management on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district?
- ii. What is the effect of working capital management on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

1.4 Conceptual Framework

Independent Variable: Working Capital Management Practices (Inventory Management, Receivables Management, Payables Management, Cash Management)

Mediating Variables: Solvency Management

Dependent Variable: Business Performance (Business Growth)

Figure 1.1 Conceptual Framework

1.5 Theoretical Framework

Resourced-based theory aspires to explain the internal sources of a firm's sustained competitive advantage (Kraaijenbrink, Spender and Groen, 2010). It was Penrose who established the foundations of the resourced-based view as a theory (Roos and Roos, 1997). Penrose first provides a logical explanation to the growth rate of the firm by clarifying the causal relationships among firm resources, production capability and performance.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study of working capital management practices and business performance of SMEs provides points out into Working capital management practices are significant facets of financial management. The study of working capital management practices and business performance of SMEs provides insights into the practicable and required growth design.

Ahmed (2016) SMEs dominate industrial scene in developing countries, their profitability understanding is very significant to the government, entrepreneurs, research institutions and the community.

2. Literature Review

Khrawish (2019) defines working capital management as the process of managing a company's short-term assets and liabilities to ensure it has enough liquidity to meet its short-term obligations and operating expenses. It involves managing inventory, accounts receivable, accounts payable, and cash to optimize the company's working capital position. working capital management (WCM) is one of the most crucial financial choices. The most advantageous and efficient WCM strategy influences performance and liquidity while increasing corporate value. The primary objective of WCM is to achieve optimal balance among its components as a part of the overall corporate strategy to increase value for shareholders. WCM, or working capital management, is a crucial component of financial management and comprises choices about the quantity, composition, and financing of current assets. For SMEs, particularly in the manufacturing sector, solvency management is important to ensure growth. Gupta and Singh (2018) states, Poor solvency management can lead to financial distress, loss of credibility with suppliers and creditors, and ultimately, bankruptcy.

Solvency is closely linked with WCM, as poor liquidity management can lead to insolvency if businesses fail to meet their short-term obligations, thereby accumulating debt and eroding their financial base (Banda and Moyo, 2022). Studies have shown that effective WCM improves solvency by ensuring that businesses maintain optimal debt levels, invest in profitable ventures, and reduce their reliance on external financing (Ghosh & Maji, 2004).

In the context of SMEs in Kitwe's manufacturing sector, solvency management becomes particularly important due to the sector's capital-intensive nature. These firms require significant investment in machinery, raw materials, and labor, which often strains their financial resources (Banda & Moyo, 2022). The main areas of focus for WCM are the size, make up, and financing of current assets and liabilities. The goal of working capital management (WCM) is to keep working capital at a level that will allow the company to run profitably and effectively. By doing this, the company makes sure that limited resources are utilized most effectively (Nazir, 2019). Furthermore, effective working capital management techniques are crucial for maximizing firm value for a micro finance institution (Pike 2017). It is the accumulation of enough cash balances from which the microfinance business can lend to the SMEs customer segments who usually depend on micro finance borrowing for their working capital needs. Several empirical studies have examined the relationship between WCM and business performance, particularly in SMEs.

For instance, a study by Padachi (2006) found that efficient management of working capital components, such as inventory and receivables, significantly improves profitability in SMEs. The study emphasized the importance of maintaining a balance between liquidity and profitability, suggesting that firms with excessive liquidity may miss out on investment opportunities, while those with insufficient liquidity may face financial distress (Padachi, 2006).

Torky (2020) studied the effect of inventory management on financial performance. According to the data, inventory management has a strong link to a company's profitability, implying that good inventory management leads to better profits, while poor inventory management leads to poor financial performance. The investigation used a case study, which revealed a methodological flaw. To close the gap, the causal research design was used.

Teruel and Solano (2009) aimed at investigating the effect of working capital management on firm profitability, using a sample of 8,872 small and medium size European companies. They found that reducing inventory and average collection periods affect positively the firm value, as reducing the cash conversion cycle improves the firm's profitability. Walker (2009) examined working capital management as a whole. Abuzayed (2012) In his survey of working capital policy among small manufacturing firms in the USA, the following aspects of working capital were considered; working capital policy and managing working capital components, including cash, receivable, payable and inventory management, and examined.

Anshur Et al (2018) researched the role of inventory management in financial performance of a few Mogadishu manufacturing firms. Inventory management and financial performance have a substantial positive association, according to the study. Ahmed (2016) investigated the link between inventory management and financial success at Nigerian conglomerate enterprises. Inventory management was found to be highly related to a company's profitability in the study. Both studies (Anshur, Ahmed & Dhodi, 2018; Ahmed, 2016) were done in Mogadishu and Nigeria, respectively, highlighting the need for a similar study to be undertaken locally. The impact of inventory management on Rwandan producer enterprises' financial performance was explored by Mulindabigwi and Mulyungi (2017).

The aim of the study was to assess the impact of inventory management on the financial performance of Rwandan manufacturing enterprises. Mulindabigwi and Mulyungi (2017) showed that the financial success of manufacturing organizations is closely linked with inventory management systems, IT and time.

The report focuses on the effects on financial performance of inventory management, which examines other elements of working capital and a conceptual gap.

Gasse (2021) studied the utilization of management techniques in small shoe and plastic manufacturing industries in Canada and found 64 percent of shoe and 65.4 percent of plastic businesses employed formal inventory control systems. Gasse (2021) in his study on the effect of inventory management on performance found that most of the respondents had in excess of 30 percent of their capital invested in inventory; the general standard of inventory management was poor.

Mbula E tal (2017) examined the effect of inventory management on financial performance of risk capital enterprises in Zambia. The research says inventory management has substantial repercussions for the financial success of venture capital businesses in Zambia.

The study examined both the financial performance benefits of inventory management and the moderating impact of Zambia's financial performance by government-funded risk capital companies (Banda and Moyo, 2022). Both Zambia government-funded venture capital firms were the target audience. Due to the small number of companies, the study used a census technique. The study focuses on the financial efficiency effect of stock management, leaving other metrics of labor capital that is being researched in this study, resulting in a conceptual hole (Sunday, 2011).

Mulindabigwi and Mulyungi (2017) researched on the impact of inventory management on financial efficiency has been carried out for the manufacturing companies listed in Zambia. The research was designed at examining the management of manufacturing companies' financial and inventory management on the stock exchange of Zambia in Lusaka. All generators of firms registered for the LUSE for the five-year period between 2012 and 2016 were interested in the study and the population was modest because the census was employed. The analysis revealed a strong link between the study's independent variables, namely inventory conversion time, inventory keeping costs, real inventory per year, and ideal inventory orders, and the study's dependent variable, financial performance (Banda & Moyo, 2022).

Findings can be summarized into some main points as follows: Thirty-nine percent of the company's total assets were working capital, but only 24 percent of the financial manager's time was spent on working capital. Overall, companies had an informal procedure or no written policy for working capital management. However, those that did have a written policy were probably more profitable than others (Gupta & Singh, 2018).

Mwaura (2017) studied the effect of inventory management on performance of Zambian medium and large retail supermarkets. This study took a cross-sectional approach to descriptive research. Sales, product expenses, current liabilities and current assets, total assets and long-term liabilities, earnings-before-tax and interest, balance in inventory closure, and yearly total profit were among the information collected (Gupta & Singh, 2018). According to correlational research, Large and medium Zambian retailers' sales in inventory and profitability are highly favorable and statistically significant. The context of this study was supermarkets, and the data was gathered from primary sources (Banda & Moyo, 2022).

Abel (2018) argues cash is crucial in every business in terms of enhancing its survival and prosperity. The term cash refers to the most liquid of assets, including demand deposits, money market accounts and currency holdings. The key elements of cash management are cash forecasting, balances management, administration of cash receipts and disbursements, and internal control (i.e., bank reconciliation) (Gitman, 2019). Good cash management can have a major impact on overall working capital management (Abuzayed, 2012). It is objectively used to manage and determine the optimal level of cash required for the business operation and invested in marketable, which is suitable for the nature of the business operation cycle.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research designs

The mixed-method approach will integrate both quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between working capital practices and performance outcomes. Quantitative data was gathered through structured questionnaires, while qualitative insights obtained via semi-structured interviews with SME managers. This approach enhances the validity and depth of findings by capturing statistical trends alongside contextual experiences (Musonda, 2020).

3.2 Target Population

According to the Kitwe Chamber of Commerce and Industry, there are approximately 250 Small Medium Enterprises functioning in the manufacturing sector in the district. SMEs are businesses with fewer than 100 workers and an annual revenue below ZMW 3.5 million. The targeted population included SME proprietors, financial administrators, and operations supervisors, as they hand working capital practices in a firm.

3.3 Sampling techniques

Stratified sampling is suitable because it divides the population into different strata (in this case, SME size and subsector within manufacturing), ensuring that the sample reflects the diversity of SMEs in the sector. The two strata were:

Micro enterprises

Small and medium enterprises

From each stratum, a random sample was selected to ensure that both micro and larger SMEs are represented in the study. This method allows for more precise comparisons between different types of SMEs.

3.4 Sample size determination

In Effect of working capital management on business Solvency and Growth. A case study of small and medium enterprises in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district, a sample size of 100 respondents was drawn from a total population of 250 SMEs using purposive sampling. This approach ensured the selection of participants who are directly involved in financial decision-making within their businesses. A sample size of 100 is considered adequate for statistical analysis, allowing for meaningful generalization of findings and ensuring data reliability (Brigham and Ehrhardt, 2020).

3.5 Data collection methods

The study utilized both primary and secondary data collection methods:

Primary Data: Data was collected through structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The questionnaires were distributed to SME owners, financial managers, and operational managers to gather quantitative data on their WCM practices, liquidity, and solvency management. The interviews were used to gather qualitative insights on the challenges and strategies related to WCM. These methods are chosen to ensure both depth and breadth in data collection. **Secondary Data:** Secondary data was sourced from financial reports, industry publications, and previous studies on WCM and SME performance in Zambia. This data helped to corroborate the findings from the primary data and provide a broader context for the study.

3.6 Data Analysis

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used to run these analyses. This tool allows for the rigorous analysis of relationships between variables, including WCM efficiency, solvency, and business performance. Qualitative data from the interviews was analyzed using thematic analysis, which involves identifying and interpreting patterns or themes within the data.

3.7 Triangulation

In this research, triangulation involved comparing the findings from the questionnaires, interviews, and secondary data to identify consistencies and discrepancies, thereby providing a more robust understanding of the effectiveness of WCM.

4. Findings and Discussions

4.1 Background characteristics

This section presents a graphical representation of the respondent’s demographics characteristics and the descriptive statistics are presented using pie bar and charts

4.1.1 Work Experience

Figure 1 shows that the majority of the respondents assumed the role of financial manager (68.0%) and about one third of them were accountants or similar (32.00%).

Figure 1: Work Experience

4.1.2 Years worked in the Company

Figure 2 shows that 8.00% of the respondents indicated that they have worked in their current position for a period of less than a year 19.00% of the respondents have worked in their current position for a period between 4-6 years and 73.00% of the respondents have worked in their current position for a period of between 1-3 years.

Figure 2: Years worked in current position

4.1.3 Company Size

Figure 3 has revealed that about one fifth 21% of the respondents in the study had over 50 employees, almost a similar proportion 22% of the respondents in the study had less than 10 employees and the majority had between 10 – 50 employees (57%) . refer to Figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Company size

4.2. Effects of Working Capital Management on the Solvency of SMEs in the Manufacturing Sector in Kitwe District

4.2.1 Testing for Hypothesis 1

In section hypothesis 1 of this study gets tested with Chi-square analysis and Pearson’s correlation. This hypothesis was formulated to examine the effect of working capital management on solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district

H₁: Working capital management has a significant effect on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H₀: Working capital management has no significant effect on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

lead to an increase in the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results of the chi-square also show that Working capital management is a predictor of the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector.

The results from the chi-square further confirms that working capital management has a significant effect on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

Table 1: Working capital management and the solvency of SMEs Correlation Test

		The solvency of SMEs	Working capital management
The solvency of SMEs	Pearson Correlation	1	.920**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
Working capital management	Pearson Correlation	.920**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Pearson’s correlation between working capital management and the solvency of SMEs has a Pearson’s correlation coefficient of 0.920** and the correlation is statistically significant since the Sig (2-tailed) has a p value less than 0.05. This result means that the relationship between working capital management and the solvency of SMEs is strong, because the value of the Pearson’s correlation coefficient is between 0.50 to 1.0.

This means that null hypothesis of this research (H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district) is, rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted which stated that (H_1 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district). The rejection of the null hypothesis means that an increase in working capital management will lead to an increase in the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results of the chi-square also indicate that working capital management is a predictor of the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The findings from the Pearson’s correlation between the variables has shown that working capital management has a significant effect on the solvency of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

4.3 Effects of working capital management on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

4.3.1 Testing for Hypothesis 2

In section hypothesis 2 of the study gets tested with Chi-square analysis and Pearson’s correlation. This hypothesis was formulated to establish the effect working capital management on growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H_2 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.

Table 2: Working capital management and the growth of SMEs chi -square test
Test Statistics

	The growth of SMEs	Working capital management
Chi-Square	229.150 ^a	156.500 ^b
Df	14	9
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 13.3.

The Chi-square test of association between working capital management and the growth of SMEs presented in the above table, recorded a significant (p) value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 at a 95% significance level, which indicates that working capital management and the growth of SMEs share a significant relationship. This means that null hypothesis of this research (H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis of this study is accepted which stated that (H_2 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.).

The rejection of the null hypothesis means that an increase of working capital management will lead to an increase in the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results of the chi-square also indicate that working capital management are predictor the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results from the chi-square have established that working capital management has a significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

Table 3: Working capital management and the growth of SMEs Pearson’s Correlations

		The growth of SMEs	Working capital management
The growth of SMEs	Pearson Correlation	1	.959**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
Working capital management	Pearson Correlation	.959**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Pearson’s correlations between working capital management and the growth of SMEs have a correlation coefficient of 0.959** and the correlation is statistically significant since the Sig (2-tailed) has a p value less than 0.05.

This result means that the relationship between working capital management and the growth of SMEs is strong, because the value of the Pearson’s correlation coefficient is between 0.50 to 1.0.

This means that null hypothesis of this research (H_0 : Working capital management has no significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis of this study is accepted which stated that (H_2 : Working capital management has a significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district.).

Firms that streamlined their working capital cycles demonstrated higher rates of expansion, including investments in new machinery and entry into new markets. The Pearson correlation results showed a positive and statistically significant relationship between WCM and business growth.

The rejection of the null means that an increase in working capital management will lead to an increase in the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The results of the chi-square also indicate that working capital management is a predictor of the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector. The findings from the Pearson’s correlation have shown that working capital management has a significant effect on the growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe district and the two variables share a very strong association.

Table 4: Results of hypotheses

Hypotheses statements	Statistical test used	(P) values	Result
H ₁	Chi-square, and Pearson’s correlation	P<0.05	Accepted
H ₂	Chi-square, and Pearson’s correlation	P<0.05	Accepted

According to the findings shown in Table 4.3.5, all of the hypothesis’s statements of this study were supported and validated .

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic data revealed that 68% of respondents were financial managers while 32% were accountants, indicating that the study primarily captured the perspectives of individuals directly involved in financial decision-making. In terms of experience, 73% had served in their positions for one to three years, 19% for four to six years, and 8% for less than a year, reflecting a workforce with moderate experience. Regarding firm size, 22% of respondents were from very small enterprises (less than 10 employees), 10.5% from small firms (10–50 employees), and 21% from medium-sized enterprises (51–100 employees), providing diverse insights across business scales.

4.4.2 Working Capital Management and Solvency of SMEs

The first objective aimed at examining the effect of WCM on solvency. The results showed a strong significant association, with a Pearson’s correlation coefficient of 0.920 ($p < 0.05$) (WCM-Report, 2025). This shows that effective WCM improves the financial stability of SMEs.

This finding also aligns with the literature that stresses the connection between liquidity and solvency. Ghosh and Maji (2004) argue that effective WCM practices not only secure short-term liquidity but also contribute to long-term solvency by preventing dependency on debt financing. Also, Musonda (2022), highlight that solvency management, and also supported by sound WCM, improves the financial credibility of SMEs with creditors and investors. The results also connect with empirical evidence from Padachi (2006), who concluded that debt ratio and current ratio were strongly positively related to profitability and solvency among SMEs in Kenya. In Kitwe, the study confirms that SMEs that effectively manage receivables, payables, and inventory are better able to sustain long-term financial commitments, thereby avoiding insolvency risks.

4.4.3 Working Capital Management and Growth of SMEs

The second objective was to establish the effect of WCM on the growth of SMEs. The findings showed a very strong positive correlation, with a coefficient of 0.959 ($p < 0.05$) (WCM-Report, 2025). This suggests that SMEs that manage their working capital efficiently are more likely to experience business expansion, improved market share, and increased capacity utilization. Growth in this context reflects not only financial outcomes but also operational scale and competitiveness. These findings align with the broader literature, which highlights that growth-oriented SMEs tend to adopt proactive WCM practices. For instance, Padachi (2006) argue that effective inventory and receivable management strategies enable firms to reinvest in productive activities, thereby supporting expansion.

Correspondingly, Brigham and Ehrhardt (2020). found that inventory efficiency is a noteworthy predictor of firm growth in manufacturing businesses. In Zambia, where SMEs often face challenges like limited financing and supply chain inefficiencies, effective WCM allows them to reallocate resources toward productive investment, thereby improving growth prospects. For example, SMEs that negotiate favorable credit terms with suppliers and implement just-in-time inventory practices are able to channel freed-up resources into innovation and expansion. The evidence from Kitwe SMEs confirms that WCM is a critical enabler of growth, particularly in capital-intensive manufacturing industries.

In summary, the results of this study confirm that effective WCM pointedly effects solvency and growth of SMEs in the manufacturing sector of Kitwe District. The indication strongly supports the suggestions made in the works that WCM is an important determinant of business performance, particularly in resource-constrained environments.

5. Conclusion, Recommendations and Summary

5.1 Conclusion

The evidence from statistical tests Chi-square, Pearson correlation, and regression analyses showed that WCM is not just an operational necessity but a strategic determinant of solvency and growth. Across all two objectives, the results confirmed that effective management of current assets and liabilities is central to sustaining financial health and competitiveness among SMEs.

The results further showed that solvency is closely linked to WCM practices. SMEs that relied excessively on short-term borrowing to address liquidity needs exposed themselves to long-term solvency risks. Statistical tests confirmed that WCM has a significant effect on solvency, with positive correlations indicating that efficient asset-liability management promotes long-term stability. The implication is that solvency cannot be divorced from WCM decisions. Firms that focus narrowly on immediate liquidity may endanger their capacity to service debt and sustain financial resilience over time.

Finally, the study confirmed that growth in SMEs is significantly influenced by WCM. Regression analysis showed that firms with efficient working capital cycles were more likely to expand operations, diversify product lines, and reinvest profits. Those with poor WCM practices, however, faced stagnation as liquidity and solvency challenges consumed resources that could have been channeled into expansion.

5.2 Recommendations

Built on the above conclusions, the following commendations are made to Small and Medium Enterprises, legislators, and other participants in the manufacturing sector in Kitwe District

- Foremost, in terms of solvency, SMEs need to balance short-term and long-term financing decisions. The findings showed that excessive reliance on short-term debt undermined solvency, even when liquidity temporarily improved. Managers should therefore avoid the temptation of using overdrafts or microfinance loans as the primary solution to cash flow gaps. Instead, SMEs should engage in financial planning that incorporates long-term stability, ensuring that debt structures are sustainable.
- On the other hand, the study recommends that SMEs adopt WCM practices as a strategy for business growth. Evidence from the findings demonstrated that firms with efficient WCM were better positioned to expand and reinvest profits. To this end, SMEs should focus on building strong supplier and customer relationships that enable flexible credit terms and reliable cash inflows. Moreover, reinvestment of profits into productive assets should be prioritized over short-term consumption.

5.3 Summary

Regarding solvency, the study concluded that excessive short-term borrowing weakens long-term financial stability, even when it temporarily improves liquidity. This finding corresponds with Carpenter and Johnson (1983), who cautioned that SMEs relying on short-term debt risk insolvency. The results also align with Gupta and Singh (2018), who found that firms with effective WCM report stronger solvency ratios. The difference in Kitwe arises from the limited availability of long-term financing, which forces SMEs to depend heavily on overdrafts and microfinance loans.

On growth, the study confirmed that WCM efficiency allows firms to reinvest earnings and expand operations. This supports Howorth and Westhead (2003), who noted that SMEs with structured WCM strategies achieve higher growth trajectories. Padachi (2006) also emphasized that freeing up cash through efficient working capital cycles enables reinvestment and expansion, a finding mirrored in Kitwe. However, the study found that external factors such as inflation and high borrowing costs still limit growth, diverging from studies in more stable economies where internal WCM improvements directly translate to expansion.

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